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Mustaqil ta'lim bo'lajak muxandis mas'uliyatining muxim asosi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak muxandis faolligini oshirish, ijtimoiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda mustaqil ta'limning roli va uni shakllantirishning dolzarb masalalari to'g'risida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: faollik, ijtimoiy kompetentlik, ta'lim jarayoni, mustaqil ta'lim moslashish, ijtimoiy mas'uliyat.

Самостоятельное обучение — важная основа ответственности будущего инженера.

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Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается роль самостоятельного образования в повышении активности будущих инженеров и развитии их социальной компетентности и важные вопросы ее формирования.

Ключевые слова: активность, социальная компетентность, образовательный процесс, самостоятельная образовательная адаптация, социальная ответственность.

Self-study is an important basis for the responsibility of a future engineer.

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Annotation. This article discusses the role of independent education in increasing the activity of future engineer and developing their social competence and important issues of its formation.

Keywords: activity, social competence, educational process, independent educational adaptation, social responsibility.

Talaba-yoshlar ijtimoiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish mahorat va ishbilarmonlik bilan ko'pgina ehtiyojlarini qondira oladigan bo'lajak mutaxassisni voyaga yetkazishdir.

Bu maqsadni amalga oshirishda talaba mustaqil ta'limi katta rol o'ynaydi. Ayniqsa, texnika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talaba ijtimoiy kompetensiyasini rivojlantirish muxim masalalardan biri bo'lib, bu borada mustaqil ta'lim imkoniyatlaridan unumli foydalanish katta ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Mustaqil ta'limning eng muxim xususiyati, unda talaba ta'lim markaziga chiqadi, o'quv jarayoni sifati oshadi, talabada ijtimoiy kompetensiya elementlari rivojlanadi, mehnat bozoriga erkin kirib borish imkoni yuzaga keladi.

Talabalar o'qituvchining bevosita ishtirokisiz yoki bilvosita boshqaruvida, u bergan vazifa, darslik asosida individual bajaradigan ishi mustaqil ish xisoblanadi. Talabalarning mustaqil ishi o'quv jarayonining ajralmas qismidir.

Talabalarning ta'lim olishda an'anaviy o'qitish usulidan mustaqil faoliyatiga katta e'tibor berib borish asosiy yetakchi g'oyadir. Mustaqil ta'lim bu talabani uz xoliga tashlab qo'yish emas, balki pedagog tomonidan muntazam boshqariladigan talabalarning mustaqil faoliyatidir.

Talabalar mustakil ta'limidan ko'zlangan asosiy maqsadlar quyidagilardan iborat:

- yangi bilim olish usullarini egallash, jarayonlarni mustaqil taxil qila olish;
- auditoriyadagi mashg'ulotlarda olgan bilimlarini mustaxkamlash, chuqurlashtirish, kengaytirish va tartibga solish;

- me'yoriy-xuquqiy aktlar, ma'lumotlar va maxsus adabiyotlar bilan ishlashni o'rganish;
- o'quv materiallarini mustaqil o'rganish;
- faolligi, bilim orttirishi, ijodiy tashabbusi, mas'uliyati va tartibligini rivojlantirish;
- olgan bilimlarini amaliyotda ko'llay olishni shakllantirish;
- mustaqil fikr yuritish, o'z-o'zini o'stirish, o'zining rejasini amalga oshirishni shakllantirish;
- tadqiqot qila olish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish.

Mustaqil ta'limning asosiy sharti talaba bajarayotgan mustaqil ishining o'qituvchi uchun emas, balki o'zi uchun, o'z kelajagidagi muvaffaqiyatini ta'minlashining asosiy omili ekanligini tushunishi kerak. Talaba olayotgan bilimi natijasiga uzi mas'ulligini anglashi zarur. Bundan ko'rinadiki, mustaqil ta'lim talabada ijtimoiy kompetensiyaning muxim elementi-mas'uliyatni shakllantiradi.

Mas'uliyatni his qilgan talaba ishini doimo puxta rejalashtirib, uning sabab-oqibatlarini oldindan tasavvur qila oladi va zarur natijaga erishish uchun butun kuch va salohiyatini safarbar etishga qodir bo'ladi.

Mustaqil ta'lim talabada faoliyatga yuqori darajadagi tayyorgarlik, mustaqil ravishda qarorlar qabul qila olish, belgilangan vazifalarni bajarish uchun ma'lumotlarni taxlil qilish va ular orasidan kerakligini tanlab olish, bu ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlay olish, muvaffaqiyatli foydalanish, natijaga nisbatan javobgarlik kabi sifatlarni muvaffaqiyatli o'zlashtirishning dastlabki bosqichidir.

Mustaqil ta'limning sifati va samaradorligi o'qituvchining bevosita raxbarligi, nazorati, ko'magiga xam bog'liq bo'lib, buning uchun avvalo o'qituvchi mustaqil ta'lim fakatgina talaba uchun emas, balki o'zi uchun xam kerak ekanligi, o'zining pedagogik funksiyalarini osonlashtirish, mustaqil fikr yurita oladigan talabalar bilan muloqotda bo'lib, o'z bilimini boyitish va kelajda xizmat pog'onalarida o'sishini ta'minlashini anglashi lozim. Mustaqil ta'limdan manfaatdorlik, o'qituvchida xam ijtimoiy kompetensiyani rivojlantirib boradi, xususan faoliyatga mas'uliyatli bo'lishga majbur qiladi, natijada talaba bilan doimiy muloqotga tayyorlik xissi, talaba bilan xamkorlikka moyillik kuchayadi.

Shu bilan bir katorada, o'qituvchining o'quv jarayonida talabalar bilan xamkorligi, ularning mustaqil ta'limga ishonchini shakllantirishi, o'qitishning yangi pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanayotganini ko'rsata olishi, ma'ruzalarni

a'naviy, ya'ni faqatgina ma'lumot berish bilan chegaralanmasdan, balki muammoli interaktiv usulda olib borishi kutilayotgan ijobiy natijalarga olib keladi.

Mustaqil ta'limdan talaba va o'qituvchining birdek manfaatdorligi, nafaqat ta'lim sifatini oshiradi, kelajakda raqobatbardosh kadr tayyorlanishiga, shuningdek, oliy ta'lim tizimidan korrupsiyaning butkul yo'qolishiga xam xizmat qiladi.

Mustaqil ta'lim orqali ta'lim sifati oshar ekan, o'qituvchi va talabada mas'uliyat xissi kuchayar ekan, ijtimoiy kompetensiya yanada rivojlanar ekan, korrupsion xolatlarga barxam berilar ekan, biz ishonch bilan ayta olamizki, O'zbekistondagi ta'lim soxasidagi isloxotlar yaqin kelajakda o'z mevasini berib, mexnat bozorida energetika yo'nalishi bitiruvchilari ishonch bilan raqobatga kirisha oladilar, jamiyatda o'z o'rinlarini topib, davlatimiz taraqqiyotini yanada yuksakka ko'tarishga xizmat qiladilar.

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